

ABOUT THE MODELING OF THE LASER ASSISTED TAPE PLACEMENT PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In the purpose of reducing the costs, the automated manufacturing of thermoplastic composites appears to be a promising possibility. The Automated Tape Placement (ATP) is often quoted for its potential ability to produce parts *in situ*. The development of such a multi-physical process must be accompanied with appropriated modeling strategies in order to avoid a trial and error method which might not be conclusive. This paper aims at studying the establishment of the residual stresses. Two modeling approaches are detailed. The first one is an eulerian approach, in which the mechanical problem is defined in a frame attached to the laying head, where the material is convected. The second one is a more classical lagrangian approach, and the problem is defined in a frame attached the tooling. First results concerning the placement of a unique ply on a ply supposed to be at rest are shown and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Within a strategy of cost reduction, the production of parts made of thermoplastic composites is a promising possibility for the interested industrial actors. Among different processes, the Automated Tape Placement (ATP) appears to be an appealing solution. It is often quoted for its potential ability to produce parts *in situ*, avoiding an expensive time and energy consuming step of post-consolidation.

During such a process, a fiber-reinforced composite is continuously laid-down and consolidated onto the previously laid layers. While the tape is heated up by the laser, and supports the roller pressure and the tension, as illustrated in Fig. 1, it is bonded to the substrate in two steps: firstly the intimate contact, and secondly the diffusion of macromolecules across the interface.

Figure 1: Illustration of the laser-assisted ATP.

The thermal solicitation associated to the continuous bonding of the plies prevents a stress-free cooling process. The evaluation of the residual stresses has to be performed since they might have a non-negligible impact on both the mechanical properties of the composite, and on its final geometry due to the so-called springback. This paper aims at detailing and comparing two modeling strategies that have been developed in order to evaluate such stresses.

In these two models, the temperature field inside the composite is supposed to be already known, from a previous established multidimensional thermal model [1]. Within the framework of the Proper Generalized Decomposition (PGD), the temperature field is known for any spatial coordinate, and for any additional extra-coordinate (the laser power and the laying velocity for example). Moreover, while the tension of the tape is taken under consideration in this study, the influence of the compaction roller and the resulting flow of the pre-preg are not considered.

2 FIRST MODEL: AN EULERIAN APPROACH

Most of the thermal models of this process are formulated in a frame attached to the laying head, where the material is convected. Thus, the geometry and the boundary conditions do not need to be updated incrementally during the placement of the tape. It is possible to formulate a mechanical model for the calculation of the residual stresses in the same frame. But instead of computing the displacement field, the main quantity of interest becomes the velocity field.

2.1 Formulation

A way to define a mechanical problem in which the velocity field is a primal variable is to use a hypoelastic law. This law consists in a linear relation between a stress rate and the mechanical strain rate. The associated constitutive equation writes

$$\frac{\delta \bar{\sigma}}{\delta t} = \bar{C} : (\bar{D} - (\bar{v} \cdot \bar{\nabla} T) \bar{\alpha}) \quad (1)$$

where T is the temperature field, $\bar{\alpha}$ is the anisotropic thermal expansion tensor, \bar{C} is the Hooke's tensor, \bar{D} is the strain rate tensor, that constitutes an objective (frame independent) strain measure, and where an objective stress rate is applied to the stress. Indeed, the time derivative of the stress tensor has to be carefully addressed because of the large displacements involved in the frame attached to the laying head. If the stress rate is not objective, some non-physical stresses may arise. A linear combination of the lower and upper-convected derivatives, the so-called Johnson and Segalman derivative, can be considered [2]. Thus, Eq. 1 can be developed as follows. Depending on the value of the parameter a (0, 1/2, or 1), an upper-convected, corotational, or lower-convected stress rate is obtained, respectively.

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}}{\partial t} + (\bar{v} \cdot \bar{\nabla}) \bar{\sigma} + a \cdot (\bar{\sigma} \cdot \bar{\nabla} \bar{v}^T + \bar{\nabla} \bar{v} \cdot \bar{\sigma}) + (1-a) \cdot (-\bar{\nabla} \bar{v}^T \cdot \bar{\sigma} - \bar{\sigma} \cdot \bar{\nabla} \bar{v}) = \bar{C} : (\bar{D} - (\bar{v} \cdot \bar{\nabla} T) \bar{\alpha}) \quad (2)$$

Neglecting the inertia the balance of the linear momentum gives, classically, Eq. 3. Eq. 2 and 3 constitute the non-linear set of equations to be solved.

$$\text{div}(\bar{\sigma}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

The boundary conditions associated to the mechanical equilibrium are represented Fig. 2. At the level of the tape, the tension is prescribed with a Neumann boundary condition. At the opposite side, the outflow of the domain, the velocity is set equal to the process laying velocity \bar{v}_L . At the bottom of the domain, where the material is in contact with the tooling, the same Dirichlet boundary conditions are prescribed. As the constitutive equation is hyperbolic, the quantity $\bar{\sigma} \cdot \bar{n}$ (inflow condition) must be given at all the regions where the quantity $\bar{v} \cdot \bar{n}$ is negative, with \bar{n} the outward unit vector, i.e. where

the matter is entering inside the domain. This can be performed locally, depending on the values of the velocity field at all the edges of the elements which contain at least one edge on the boundary of the domain (the top, the right-hand side, the bottom of the tape and the top of the substrate at the tape/substrate interface, in Fig. 2).

While the mechanical equilibrium can be solved with a classical Finite Elements Method (FEM), the hyperbolic nature of the constitutive equation needs specific treatments. A promising numerical method is the Discontinuous Galerkin (DG) method, with local stabilization through the definition of appropriated fluxes.

Figure 2: Geometry and boundary conditions.

The real advantage of such a formulation is that the tape and the substrate are naturally bonded together at the nip point, because of the nature of the geometry. And finally, the state of stress at the outflow, where the material has recovered the room temperature, described the residual stresses which arise from the bonding of the (relatively hot) tape to the (relatively cold) substrate.

Under the steady state hypothesis, the expression of the stress with respect to the velocity field is not explicit. So that the non-linear system of equations cannot be reduced to a single equation. The direct consequence is that the stress tensor field must be considered as an unknown of the problem. Then, the velocity field does not appear naturally in the mechanical equilibrium equation (Eq. 3). The two possible approaches to solve the system of equation are:

- on one side, to use a decoupled formulation, which can be defined only in the transient regime,
- on the other side, to use a coupled formulation, which can be defined in the steady state regime.

2.2 Decoupled numerical scheme

In the transient regime, the non-explicit relation between the stress and the velocity can be circumvented, following G. D'Avino and M.A. Hulsen [3], by writing the constitutive equation with an explicit description of the time derivative of the stress, see Eq. 4.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\bar{\sigma}}^{n+1} = \bar{\bar{\sigma}}^n + \Delta t \cdot \{ & -(v^{n+1} \cdot \nabla) \bar{\bar{\sigma}}^n - a \cdot (\bar{\bar{\sigma}}^n \cdot \bar{\bar{\nabla}}_v^{n+1,T} + \bar{\bar{\nabla}}_v^{n+1} \cdot \bar{\bar{\sigma}}^n) + \\ & (1-a) \cdot (\bar{\bar{\nabla}}_v^{n+1,T} \cdot \bar{\bar{\sigma}}^n + \bar{\bar{\sigma}}^n \cdot \bar{\bar{\nabla}}_v^{n+1}) + \bar{\bar{C}} : \bar{\bar{D}}^{n+1} \} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Thus, knowing the velocity and the stress at time t_n , Eq. 4 gives an explicit candidate for the stress at time t_{n+1} . This candidate, which contains the velocity field at time t_{n+1} , can be inserted in Eq. 3 to compute this velocity field. This velocity field can then be used in Eq. 2 to compute the stress tensor field at time t_{n+1} with an explicit or implicit time integration scheme.

The strong weak point of this approach is that the convergence in time is mandatory to reach the steady state solution.

2.3 Coupled numerical scheme

In order to avoid performing a transient calculation, the steady state of stress can be obtained using a coupled numerical scheme. In order to assemble the non-linear and discrete system of equations associated to the constitutive equation (Eq. 2), the velocity field has to be assumed. In the same time, the discrete and linear system of equations associated to the mechanical equilibrium (Eq. 3) can be assembled. The full system of equation can be inverted to compute new stress and velocity fields. From this new velocity field, a new system can be assembled and solved, and this procedure can be repeated until convergence. Using this Picard-type approach, the steady state velocity and stress fields can be computed.

This scheme has been implemented, and even if it appears to be very attractive compared to the decoupled formulation, strong oscillations have been observed in the obtained solution. Indeed, it is known that coupled formulations, whose resolution might be equivalent to search for a saddle-point, may be stable only under a certain *infsup* condition [4]. Thus, the approximation spaces of the variables should be chosen carefully.

2.4 Stabilization

In both formulations (decoupled and coupled), taking under consideration real material properties has systematically been a cause of divergence, and the use of specific stabilization techniques becomes mandatory. In the context of modeling viscoelastic fluid flows, this phenomenon is well known, and constitutes the origin of the development of the more stable EVSS (Elastic-Viscous-Split-Stress) formulation, by Rajagopalan et al. [5]. The alternative DEVSS (for Discrete-EVSS) introduced by R. Guenette and M. Fortin [6] can also be used, as did, for example, G. D'Avino and M.A. Hulsen [3]. In this formulation, an additional variable equal to the velocity gradient in the sense of Galerkin is considered, and a stabilizing term is added in the weak form of the momentum balance equation, multiplied by a stabilization parameter.

2.5 Limit of this approach: a High Weissenberg Number issue?

This DEVSS formulation has been implemented, and the stabilization has been observed. But it has been noticed that when the mesh size became too small, the stabilization was possible only for dramatically high values of the stabilization parameter. So that non-physical body forces (due to the DEVSS) lead to non-physical solutions. As no convergence can be reached without any stabilization, the development of a model containing viscoelastic effects is under progress.

When modeling a viscoelastic fluid flow, the elastic component τ of the stress of an Oldroyd-B fluid follows Eq. 5, where λ is a characteristic time of the fluid, and η a viscosity coefficient.

$$\frac{1}{\lambda} \tau + \frac{\delta \tau}{\delta t} = \frac{2 \cdot \eta}{\lambda} \overline{D} \quad (5)$$

The Weissenberg number, We , is a dimensionless number, and is the ratio of the relaxation time and a specific process time. It is well known in the community that beyond some critical values of We , a vast majority of the numerical schemes fails to provide solutions [7].

In the hypoelastic model, the term proportional to the stress is equal to zero. In some way, this corresponds to have an infinite relaxation time (purely elastic case), and thus, an infinite Weissenberg number. This remark underlines how much the use of a hypoelastic law is extremely constrained from a numerical point of view.

3 SECOND MODEL: A LAGRANGIAN APPROACH

Another possibility to model the establishment of the residual stresses is a lagrangian approach, in a frame attached to the tooling. The matter is not convected anymore, and the placement of the tape is modeled by incrementally updating the geometry, because of the continuous bonding the tape and the substrate. This is illustrated in Fig. 3. The roller is only shown to indicate the position of the nip point on the figure. The length r_f of the considered domain has been taken such that it is as small as possible for numerical cost considerations, and high enough to identify a region in which the state of stress is relatively constant after the placement of the ply.

Figure 3: Illustration of the incremental model

3.1 Formulation

The definition of a mechanical problem in this type of frame is more classical. In a thermoelastic model, the stress is proportional to the mechanical strain and follows Eq. 6, where $\bar{\varepsilon}$ is the total strain, equal to the symmetric part of the gradient of the displacement field. The mechanical equilibrium is identical to the equation considered in the hypoelastic case, Eq. 3. The associated boundary conditions are very similar to the one described previously, replacing the prescribed velocity by a prescribed displacement field, equal to zero.

$$\bar{\sigma} = \bar{C} : \left[\bar{\varepsilon} - \Delta T \cdot \bar{\alpha} \right] \quad (6)$$

Rigorously, the displacement field and the stress field satisfy the following set of equations,

$$\bar{\sigma} = 0 \quad (7.1)$$

$$\overset{=}{\sigma}^{n+1} = \overset{=}{\sigma}^n + \overset{=}{C} : \left[\overset{=}{\varepsilon}^{n+1} - (T^{n+1} - T^n) \cdot \overset{=}{\alpha}^{n+1} \right] \quad (7.2)$$

$$\text{div}(\overset{=}{\sigma}^{n+1}) = 0 \quad (7.3)$$

where $(T^{n+1} - T^n)$ refers to the thermal solicitation experienced by the material between the state at the instant n and the state at the instant $(n+1)$. The calculation is stopped when a certain region of the domain has seen the laser coming and leaving, and has recovered the reference temperature.

From the numerical point of view, the FEM can be used. For the purpose of avoiding the addition of incremental interpolation errors, the stresses should be added incrementally exactly where they are known at each iteration, i.e. at the integration points. Moreover, as the final quantity of interest is the stress, second order elements might be considered.

3.2 Calculation for a ply laid down on a unique ply supposed to be stress-free

As already mentioned, the temperature field is already known from a previous thermal model of the ATP process. The appearance of this temperature field and the consequent thermal solicitation (difference between the temperature fields at two consecutive instants) are shown in Fig. 4. The material properties needed in the Hooke tensor and in the anisotropic thermal expansion tensor have been computed using the Halpin-Tsai homogenization method, with the properties of carbon fibers and of a polymer whose Young modulus drops after a certain glass transition temperature from a reasonable value to a very small value (0.1 MPa for example).

Figure 4: Thermal solicitation during the iterative calculation.

At the final step of the iterative procedure, a region which undergoes a constant state of stress can be observed. The XY and YY components of the stress tensor field are very close to zero, while the XX component is not null, and is plotted as a function of the relative thickness (y direction) in Fig. 5, for two meshes.

For both meshes, only one common edge of two elements belonging to the tape and the substrate has been bonded per iteration. This means that for the finer mesh, which contains elements with an aspect ratio of 4, twice as many iterations have been performed compared to the calculation made with the mesh containing elements with an aspect ratio of 8. As we can see, the resulting state of stress has not yet reached any mesh convergence. Finer calculations have not been performed because of the relatively high numerical cost. Indeed, each time the mesh is refined, they are not only more elements and degrees of freedom, but also more iterations to be computed. So that considering twice more elements implies a total computing time four times higher, if the number of elements bonded per iteration is kept equal to 1.

Figure 5: Final XX component of the stress as a function of the relative thickness, for two meshes.

If the placement of the tape was possible using an ideally isothermal process, the following final state of stress would be homogeneous and equal to 0 in the bottom ply, and homogeneous and equal to the tension stress in the upper ply. But as it can be noticed in Fig. 5, while the bottom ply keeps being at rest, the upper ply is under compression. As the associated thermal expansion coefficient in the x direction is negative, the upper ply would like to expand after it has been bonded to the substrate. But as the substrate is fixed to the tooling, it does not allow such a kinematics to appear. Thus, the upper ply, in this thermoelastic framework, must undergo some compression. In this model, the influence of the tension is linear. So that if more and more tension is considered during the placement, the upper ply could be under tension.

4 CONCLUSION

With the purpose of studying the establishment of residual stresses during the ATP of thermoplastic composites, two modeling approaches have been detailed and discussed. The first eulerian approach, in which the mechanical problem is formulated in a frame attached to the laying head, is very attractive since it would allow capturing directly the steady state stress solution, with a unique geometry. But the hyperbolic nature of the constitutive equation, related to its non-linearity and instability make it very difficult to obtain converged results, even using advanced stabilization techniques such as DEVSS formulations.

The second lagrangian approach, in which the mechanical problem is formulated in a frame attached to the tooling, is a lot more classical. Indeed, a well-defined sequence of thermoelastic mechanical equilibriums has to be solved using FEM (for example), adding the state of stress at the integration points. Unfortunately, in this frame, the continuous bonding must be discretized, by updating incrementally the thermal loading as well as the geometry. This introduces a numerical error which has to be controlled, and implies relatively high computational cost. Thus, the actual implementation and method did not allow us to simulate the placement of a consequent laminate. First results of the placement of a unique ply have been shown and discussed. After some optimization of the assembling and the inversion of the linear system, further simulations with more plies will be performed. With these improvements, the influence of the thickness of the composite or the geometry will be studied.

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